

Game of Life

Utkarsh R ,B.Ed ,Integral University Lucknow Uttar Pradesh India

**Game of Life
(Poem)**

I had faith on you like I had on my life,
I thought my fate is linked with you,
But actually your selfishness was linked with me.

I still remember the day you met me,
But today I remember the way you left me.

When you ruined my trust ,
I was having no feeling of disgust,
Because I lost the one who was temporary part of my life but,
You have lost the one who was permanent part of your life.